

Cell Line Characterization

Cell Line ID:
Passage #:
Specimen Type:
Indication for Study:

Lab #:
PI:
Contact Person:
Email:
Address:

Test Code: Date Received:
Account #: Date Reported:
PO #: Time in Culture:

Additional copies sent to:

Banding Technique: Band Resolution:
Metaphases Counted: Analyzed: Karyotyped:

RESULTS:

Non-clonal Aberrations:

INTERPRETATION: